

Land surface temperature (LST) metadata related to observations and modelling (primarily related to): London, UK

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Table of Contents

1.	Background	1
1.1.	Access to these files prior to embargo date	1
2.	Zenodo Archives	2
2.1.	Overview	2
2.2.	DART_XXX	2
2.3.	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip	2
2.4.	London: Optris_runDailyClassification\3DtemperatureExtrapolation\2017\239	3
2.5.	London: Optris_runDailyClassification\3DtemperatureExtrapolation\2017\	4
2.6.	London: DART Miscellaneous	4
2.7.	Filenames in directory structure	4
2.8.	Zenodo archives in DOI order	5
3.	Awards/Grants that have supported this research	6
4.	Related Publications	7

1. Background

This document provides background information for a large number of Zenodo Archives (section 2) associated with observations and modelling of urban land surface temperatures, predominately in London (UK).

Details of Optris sensors used in London are provided at:

- Grimmond, S., Benjamin, K., Gabey, A., Kotthaus, S., Morrison, W., Offerle, B., Pauscher, L., Ward, H., zum Berge, K., Brown, J., Crawford, B., Saunders, B., Sun, T., & Warren, E. (2022). Multi-city Urban Hydroclimate Data (MUHD) - Meta data for observations Release 2022-03-21. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13134582>

The data have been used in a number of papers (section 4). The work was made possible by a number of grants (Section 3). These are gratefully acknowledged.

A wide range of people have contributed to this work. They are (hopefully) all identified in individual papers (section 4) and the Grimmond et al. (2022) report.

1.1. Access to these files prior to embargo date

If you would like access to these files prior to the embargo date please contact Dr William Morrison and/or Prof Sue Grimmond either directly or via urbisphere_ur@gmail.com

Please cite the individual Zenodo Archives (section 2) and the publications (section 4).

Note: access can only be provided to data not the actual DART (Discrete anisotropic radiative transfer) model. To obtain access to the DART model visit the [DART](https://dart.omp.eu/#/) website: <https://dart.omp.eu/#/>

2. Zenodo Archives

2.1. Overview

There are three groups or archive types:

- 1) DART- these are related to numerical modelling with the DART Radiative Transfer Model
- 2) Optris- these are more directly related to the observations but are also informed by modelling
- 3) Miscellaneous – three small archives (section 2.6)

For the first two types there are two sets of archives

- 1) DART – various versions of the model (section 2.2), with one version 5-7-5_1126 having many more files (section 2.3)
- 2) Optris – these are organised by time in 2017. Most of these are for individual days (section 2.4), but for one day (239) there are a large number of archives (section 0).

2.2. DART_XXX

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo	Contents
.14603732	DART_5-6-7_v992.zip
.14603732	DART_5-6-7_v998.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-0_v1011.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-0_v1017.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-0_v1018.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-0_v1021.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-0_v1046.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-4_1091.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-4_1094.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-4_1101.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-4_1103.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-4_1082.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-5_1141.zip
.14603732	DART_5-7-6_1147.zip
.14603732	DART_5-8-0_1211.zip
.14603732	DART-5-7-1_1058.zip
.14603732	DART-5-7-3_1075.zip

2.3. DART_5-7-5_1126.zip

As the top directory has the order of 120 GB in one zip file, which too large for a single Zenodo, archive, this is split into 5 files stored in four archives (i.e. 001- 005, 4 DOI). These were files were created with <https://www.7-zip.org/> software.

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo	Title	Contents
14795566	London: DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.001	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.001
14796122	London: DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.002	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.002
14800322	London: DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.003	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.003
14839910	London: DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.004, DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.005	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.004
14839910	London: DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.004, DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.005	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.005

2.4. London: Optris_runDailyClassification\3DtemperatureExtrapolation\2017\239

These files are for day of year 239 (Saturday 27 August 2017)

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo	filename – time of day
.14721753	010000.zip
.14721753	020000.zip
.14721753	025000.zip
.14721753	030500.zip
.14721753	040500.zip
14720193	050500.zip
.14720193	060500.zip
.14743333	070500.zip
.14743333	080500.zip
.14743333	090500.zip
.14747646	100500.zip
.14747646	110500.zip
.14748541	120500.zip
.14755406	130500.zip
.14755406	150000.zip
.14754202	150500.zip
.14754202	170000.zip
.14754202	180000.zip
.14754202	190000.zip
.14748541	200000.zip
.14748541	210000.zip
.14748541	220000.zip
.14748541	230000.zip
.14748541	235500.zip

2.5. London: Optris_runDailyClassification\3DtemperatureExtrapolation\2017\

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo	Day of Year in 2017
.14720193	235.zip
.14720193	236.zip
.14756933	237.zip
.14720193	238.zip
.14720193	240.zip
.14721753	241.zip
.14721753	242.zip
.14721753	243.zip
.14721753	244.zip
.14721753	245.zip
.14721753	249.zip
.14721769	250.zip
.14721769	251.zip
.14721769	252.zip
.14721769	253.zip
.14756933	254.zip
.14756933	255.zip
.14756933	256.zip
.14756933	258.zip
.14756933	260.zip
.14756933	262.zip
.14756933	263.zip
.14756933	265.zip
.14756933	266.zip
.14756933	268.zip
.14756933	269.zip
.14756933	270.ZIP

2.6. London: DART Miscellaneous

Morrison, W., & Grimmond, S. (2025). London: DART Miscellaneous [Data set].
Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14834316>

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo	Filename
14834316	Student.zip
14834316	Anisotropy.zip
14834316	DARTfiles.zip

2.7. Filenames in directory structure

These files were originally used on RACC. The complete file listing with file size are given in the file: hv867657_files.txt. This may help identify where particular files should be located in this set of linked archives.

2.8. Zenodo archives in DOI order

The following lists the files archived by numerical order based on DOI

Zenodo	Group type	file
5 13133952	Metadata	MUHD overview
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-6-7_v992.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-6-7_v998.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-0_v1011.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-0_v1017.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-0_v1018.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-0_v1021.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-0_v1046.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-4_1091.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-4_1094.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-4_1101.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-4_1103.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-4-1082.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-5_1141.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-7-6_1147.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART_5-8-0_1211.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART-5-7-1_1058.zip
1 14603732	DART	DART-5-7-3_1075.zip
2 14839910	DART_5-7-5_1126	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.004
2 14839910	DART_5-7-5_1126	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.005
2 14796122	London: DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.002	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.002
2 14795566	London: DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.001	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.001
2 14800322	London: DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.003	DART_5-7-5_1126.zip.003
3 14721769	Optris_runDailyClassification	250.zip
3 14721769	Optris_runDailyClassification	251.zip
3 14721769	Optris_runDailyClassification	252.zip
3 14721769	Optris_runDailyClassification	253.zip
3 14743333	Optris_runDailyClassification	070500.zip
3 14743333	Optris_runDailyClassification	080500.zip
3 14743333	Optris_runDailyClassification	090500.zip
3 14755406	Optris_runDailyClassification	130500.zip
3 14755406	Optris_runDailyClassification	150000.zip
3 14747646	Optris_runDailyClassification	100500.zip
3 14747646	Optris_runDailyClassification	110500.zip
3 14754202	Optris_runDailyClassification	150500.zip
3 14754202	Optris_runDailyClassification	170000.zip
3 14754202	Optris_runDailyClassification	180000.zip
3 14754202	Optris_runDailyClassification	190000.zip
3 14720193	Optris_runDailyClassification	050500.zip
3 14720193	Optris_runDailyClassification	060500.zip
3 14720193	Optris_runDailyClassification	235.zip
3 14720193	Optris_runDailyClassification	236.zip
3 14720193	Optris_runDailyClassification	238.zip
3 14720193	Optris_runDailyClassification	240.zip
3 14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	010000.zip
3 14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	020000.zip
3 14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	025000.zip
3 14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	030500.zip
3 14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	040500.zip
3 14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	241.zip
3 14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	242.zip

3	14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	243.zip
3	14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	244.zip
3	14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	245.zip
3	14721753	Optris_runDailyClassification	249.zip
3	14748541	Optris_runDailyClassification	120500.zip
3	14748541	Optris_runDailyClassification	200000.zip
3	14748541	Optris_runDailyClassification	210000.zip
3	14748541	Optris_runDailyClassification	220000.zip
3	14748541	Optris_runDailyClassification	230000.zip
3	14748541	Optris_runDailyClassification	235500.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	237.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	254.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	255.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	256.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	258.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	260.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	262.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	263.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	265.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	266.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	268.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	269.zip
3	14756933	Optris_runDailyClassification	270.ZIP
6	14766133	Overview	This document
7	14834316	MIsc	Student.zip
7	14834316	MIsc	Anisotropy.zip
7	14834316	MIsc	DARTfiles.zip

3. Awards/Grants that have supported this research

Organizations funding from:

UKRI: UK Research and Innovation

EC: European Commission

Grant title	Number	From
Data Assimilation for the REsilient City (DARE)	EP/P002331/1	UKRI
urbisphere - coupling dynamic cities and climate	855005	EC
Climate service for resilience to overheating risk in Colombo, Sri Lanka: a multi-scale mapping approach (COSMA)	NE/S005889/1	UKRI
IUS-UM100	MO Strategic Priorities Fund Climate Resilience Programme	Met Office
URBANFLUXES — URBan ANthropogenic heat FLUX from Earth observation Satellites	637519	EC

4. Related Publications

- Grimmond, S., Benjamin, K., Gabey, A., Kotthaus, S., Morrison, W., Offerle, B., Pauscher, L., Ward, H., zum Berge, K., Brown, J., Crawford, B., Saunders, B., Sun, T., & Warren, E. (2022). Multi-city Urban Hydroclimate Data (MUHD) - Meta data for observations Release 2022-03-21. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13134582>
- Grimmond, S., & Morrison, W. (2025). Land surface temperature (LST) metadata related to observations and modelling (primarily related to): London, UK. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14766133>
- Hall T, L Blunn, S Grimmond, N McCarroll, C Merchant, W Morrison, J Shonk, H Lean, M Best 2024: Utility of thermal remote sensing for evaluation of a high-resolution weather model in a city *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.4669>
- Morrison W 2019: *Urban ground-based thermography*. PhD thesis, University of Reading <https://doi.org/10.48683/1926.00089043>
- Morrison W, Grimmond S, Kotthaus S 2023: Simulating satellite urban land surface temperatures: sensitivity to sensor view angle and assumed landscape complexity *Remote Sensing of the Environment* 293:113579 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.111524>
- Morrison W, S Kotthaus S Grimmond 2021: Urban surface temperature observations from ground-based thermography: intra- and inter-facet variability *Urban Climate* 35:100748 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2020.100748>
- Morrison W, S Kotthaus; S Grimmond, A Inagaki, T Yin, J-P Gastellu-Etchegorry, M Kanda, C Merchant 2018: A novel method to obtain three-dimensional urban surface temperature from ground-based thermography *Remote Sensing of the Environment* 215:268-283 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.05.004>
- Morrison W, T Yin, N Lauret, J Guilleux, S Kotthaus, JP Gastellu-Etchegorry, L Norford, CSB Grimmond 2020: Atmospheric and emissivity correction for ground-based thermography using 3D radiative transfer modelling *Remote Sensing of the Environment* 237:111524 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.111524>
- Stretton M, W Morrison, R Hogan, S Grimmond 2022: Modelling vertically resolved shortwave radiation in urban areas: evaluation of SPARTACUS-Urban *Boundary-Layer Meteorology* 184:301–331, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10546-022-00706-9>
- Stretton MA, RJ Hogan, CSB Grimmond, W Morrison 2023: Characterising the vertical structure of buildings in cities for use in atmospheric models *Urban Climate* 50:101560 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2023.101560>
- Stretton MA, W Morrison, RJ Hogan, S Grimmond 2023: Evaluation of vertically resolved longwave radiation in SPARTACUS-Urban and the sensitivity to urban surface temperatures *Geoscientific Model Development* 16:5931- 47 <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-5931-2023>
- Xie X, Z Luo, S Grimmond, T Sun, W Morrison 2022: Impact of inter-building longwave radiative exchanges on building energy performance and indoor overheating *Building and Environment* 209:108628 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2021.108628>